

*Cross-sectoral planning decision-making
platform to foster climate action*

Guidelines for improving climate action: Insights from scenario modelling with WILIAM

Policy Brief

September 2025

H2020-LC-GD-2020-2: LC-GD-9-2-2020. Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037104.

Towards a resilient and climate-neutral society: Insights from simulating scenarios using WILLIAM

Introduction

RethinkAction project has obtained relevant modelling results based on the application of the WILLIAM Integrated Assessment Model¹, that make possible to assess the impact of different mitigation and adaptation policies with focus on European scenarios. The results show that integrated approaches in agriculture, energy, land use, and urban planning can provide substantial greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions, while also safeguarding biodiversity, food security, and social equity. This document presents two key policy outcomes for European, national, and regional policymakers.

¹ https://github.com/LOCOMOTION-h2020/WILLIAM_model_VENSIM/wiki

1. Promotion of dietary shifts combined with regenerative agriculture and sustainable land use

Context

The results of WILLIAM model highlight that a transition toward flexitarian or plant-based diets, together with regenerative agriculture, is one of the most effective strategies to reduce GHG emissions, free up land, and contribute to limit temperature increase. In high-ambition scenarios, the European Union (EU) could save up to 80 million hectares of grassland and cropland, which could be allocated to forests or other carbon-rich ecosystems, providing strong mitigation, biodiversity co-benefits and fundamental ecosystem services.

Suggested actions

- ✓ Mainstream sustainable and healthy diets by creating plant-based menus and promoting their benefits aligned with climate change.
- ✓ Support farmers in the transition, through advisory services, low-interest loans, and incentives to diversify production with crops like pulses or legumes and the diversification to agroforestry systems.
- ✓ Clear and transparent food labelling for consumers to foster sustainable dietary choices.
- ✓ Relocate freed-up land toward reforestation, ecosystem restoration, or alternative sustainable crops, aligned with the EU Nature Restoration Law and Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming (CRCF) regulations.

Expected impact

- ✓ Deep reduction in agricultural emissions and pressure on natural resources.
- ✓ Increased biodiversity and strengthened potential of carbon sinks.
- ✓ Improved public health through healthier diets.
- ✓ Long-term resilience of the agricultural sector and increased EU protein self-sufficiency.

Relevant actors to guide the decisions

- ✓ European Commission (EC), Member States, Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) governance bodies.

- ✓ Farmers, agri-food sector, civil society organizations.
- ✓ Regional and local authorities responsible for land-use planning.

2. Integrated renewable energy deployment with large-scale ecosystem restoration and multi-level governance

Context

The results from WILIAM model, demonstrates that ambitious renewable energy expansion, when combined with ecosystem restoration (e.g., afforestation, grassland restoration), achieves greater mitigation than pursuing energy or land policies in isolation. Medium-to-high integration scenarios nearly doubled land-sector emission cuts compared to renewables alone, delivering up to 0.3 °C avoided warming by 2060 at global level. Coordinated multi-level governance efforts could be useful to align climate, biodiversity, and food security goals.

Suggested actions

- ✓ Accelerate deployment of renewables prioritizing low-impact solutions like rooftop solar, offshore wind, and floating PV.
- ✓ Define strict siting rules to avoid land conflicts with food production and biodiversity, ensuring solar and wind expansion complements land protection.
- ✓ Implement integrated spatial planning frameworks that link National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) with land and biodiversity strategies, supported by EU and national funding.

Conclusions

The modelling exercise developed using WILIAM model, demonstrates that the integration of dietary change with regenerative land use, and renewable energy expansion with ecosystem restoration, represents two of the most robust pathways toward EU climate neutrality. Implementing these recommendations will enable Europe to deliver faster, and more sustainable climate action.

- ✓ Adopt a unified cross-sectoral strategy connecting the climate law, biodiversity strategy, and the CAP, to reward actions that deliver multiple objectives.

Expected impact

- ✓ GHG reduction from energy and land sectors.
- ✓ Increased resilience of ecosystems and reduced land-energy trade-offs.
- ✓ Greater food security through safeguarding cropland and fertile soils.
- ✓ Stronger public trust and legitimacy of the climate transition through transparent governance.

Key actors

- ✓ European Commission, national ministries of energy, agriculture, and environment.
- ✓ Regional authorities and municipalities responsible for land-use planning.
- ✓ Renewable energy developers, farmers, local communities, and NGOs.

*Images: <https://pixabay.com/>.

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